

PREDICTION OF FATIGUE DAMAGE IN HOLED COMPOSITE LAMINATES WITH EMBEDDED FBG SENSORS

A. Kadoya and S. Yashiro
Ehime University

3 Bunkyo-cho, Matsuyama, Ehime 790-8577, Japan

T. Okabe

Tohoku University

6-6-01 Aoba-yama, Aoba-ku, Sendai 980-8579, Japan

yashiro@eng.ehime-u.ac.jp

SUMMARY

This study investigates damage monitoring for a holed CFRP laminate under fatigue loading by using an embedded FBG sensor. Measured reflection spectrum of the FBG sensor changed with damage extension in the laminate. The mechanism of the change in the spectrum shape was discussed through a numerical simulation for fatigue damage extension.

Keywords: Polymer matrix composites, Fatigue, Delamination, Structural health monitoring, Finite element analysis

INTRODUCTION

CFRPs have frequently been applied to structural components because of their good mechanical properties. Damage will be generated in the composite components due to cyclic loading. Monitoring the damage extension is essential to ensure the structural safety. Moreover, damage easily accumulates near stress concentrated region, and the damage pattern is complex [1]. Although soft X-ray radiography and ultrasonic C-scan method are usually used to detect the damage, these large-scale systems involve high costs in inspection. In order to address the difficulty, fiber-optic based structural health monitoring approaches have recently been studied [2,3]. This study experimentally and numerically investigates evaluation of fatigue damage progress in holed CFRP laminates by using embedded fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensors. First, tensile fatigue tests were conducted for a holed CFRP cross-ply laminate with an embedded FBG sensor; the damage pattern near the hole and the reflection spectrum of the FBG sensor were observed in detail. Furthermore, the reflection spectrum was analyzed by a finite-element based fatigue simulation with cohesive elements and by an optical analysis for the FBG sensor. We clarified the mechanism of the change in the reflection spectrum due to the damage extension, and discussed the damage monitoring for the CFRP laminate under cyclic loading based on the information from the embedded FBG sensor. Especially, we found that the debonding of optical fiber grew as the number of cycles increased. This could limit the monitoring period in the application of FBG sensor.

EXPERIMENTS

In this study, the CFRP T700S/#2521R (Toray Industries, Inc.) cross-ply laminates were used as specimens and their stacking sequence was $[0_2/90_2]_s$. The shape of the specimens was 200 mm length and 30 mm width. The holes were made at the center of specimens. A thickness of each layer was 0.1 mm. To detect the fatigue damage near a hole, the optical fiber with an FBG sensor (Broptics Technology Inc.), which had a gage section 12.5 mm in length, was embedded into the 0° ply near the 90° ply. The surface of the optical fiber was coated by Polyimide resin with coating diameter of $150\ \mu\text{m}$. The gage section was set up 1.36 mm away from the edge of the hole. GFRP tabs were attached to the both ends of specimen in order to avoid the failure of the grip. The conditions of the fatigue test were as follows; the maximum stress was 260 MPa, the stress ratio was 0.1, and the cyclic frequency was 5 Hz. The fatigue test was stopped after a given number of cycles. Then, the reflection spectrum was measured at the mean-stress condition. After the fatigue test, damage near the hole was observed with the soft X-ray radiography. Moreover, the damage in the specimen that did not include an optical fiber was observed with the soft X-ray radiography at the interval of certain cycles.

Figure 1 depicts the damage patterns observed in experiments. The splits in 0° ply, the transverse cracks in 90° ply, and the delamination were seen in the soft X-ray photographs. As depicted in Fig. 1 at the small number of cycles, short splits and transverse cracks were generated near the hole. The splits grew in the loading direction and the number of transverse cracks increased with increasing number of cycles. The lengths of transverse cracks were small when they were generated. They grew in the width direction due to the cyclic loading, and finally attained to the edge of the specimen. After both transverse cracks and splits were sufficiently extended, the delamination was generated in 1/4 ellipse shape as depicted in Figs. 1b-1d. We compared the damage patterns in the specimen that included an FBG sensor with the damage patterns without an FBG sensor, and confirmed that the FBG sensor did not affect the damage extension.

Fig. 1 Soft X-ray photographs of the fatigue damage progress in the holed CFRP laminates.

Fig. 2 Comparison of the reflection spectrum between the experiment and the simulation. The blue line is the simulated spectrum without considering debonding of the optical fiber, and the red line is the simulated spectrum with debonding.

The measured reflection spectrum of the FBG sensor is illustrated in Fig. 2. The initial width of the reflection spectrum was 0.24 nm before the FBG sensor was embedded into the specimen, and it became broad after embedding. This broad spectrum might represent the birefringence effect due to the thermal residual strain [4]. The shape of the reflection spectrum measured at the mean-stress condition changed as the number of cycles, N , increased; the spectrum had two peaks at $N = 10^3$ (Fig. 2b), and only one peak was observed in the longer wavelength after $N = 10^4$ (Figs. 2c and 2d).

ANALYSIS

Figure 3 illustrates a finite-element model for the holed CFRP laminate of $[0_2/90_2]_s$ as an example of a simulation model. The model is separated into individual layers representing 0° ply and 90° ply. Each ply of the CFRP laminate is assumed to be an orthotropic homogeneous body. The model consists of linear-elastic, four-node Mindlin-plate elements that permit consideration of out-of-plane deformation.

In this modeling, we consider the following damage modes: (1) splitting in the 0° layer, (2) transverse cracking in the 90° layer, and (3) delamination at the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface.

Cohesive elements are used to express these damage modes. In order to introduce the effect of cyclic loading, Kachanov's damage progress law [5] was modified, and was applied to the residual strength of cohesive elements. To reduce the calculation cost, we did not adopt an incremental analysis capturing the detailed loading path of the cycles. Damage was assumed to accumulate only when the maximum stress was applied.

Fig. 3 Layer-wise finite element model of the cross-ply laminate with an open hole and with an embedded optical fiber.

Furthermore, damage accumulated during one loading cycle could be slight. Therefore, we adopted the approximate method for evaluating the damage accumulation during every several cycles.

A cohesive element utilizes the following relation between traction and relative displacement of the crack surface. The relation between the traction \mathbf{T} and the relative displacement Δ is defined using the residual-strength parameter for the elements, s , proposed by Geubelle [6].

$$\mathbf{T} = \begin{Bmatrix} T_n \\ T_t \\ T_b \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{s}{1-s} \frac{\tau_{n\max}}{\Delta_{nc}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{s}{1-s} \frac{\tau_{t\max}}{\Delta_{tc}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{s}{1-s} \frac{\tau_{b\max}}{\Delta_{bc}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \Delta_n \\ \Delta_t \\ \Delta_b \end{Bmatrix} = \bar{\mathbf{D}}_{coh} \Delta \quad (1)$$

Subscripts n , t and b indicate the cracking modes of normal tensile deformation, in-plane shear, and out-of-plane shear. $\tau_{i\max}$ and Δ_{ic} ($i = n, t, b$) are the strength and the critical relative displacement in each cracking mode. The term “strength” represents a criterion for starting the damage process in cohesive elements. The critical relative displacement is the relative displacement with no traction in the cohesive element. The critical relative displacement is defined based on the critical energy release rate, G_{ic} ($i = \text{I, II, III}$), as follows.

$$\Delta_{nc} = \frac{2G_{Ic}}{\tau_{n\max} s_{ini}}, \quad \Delta_{tc} = \frac{2G_{IIc}}{\tau_{t\max} s_{ini}}, \quad \Delta_{bc} = \frac{2G_{IIIc}}{\tau_{b\max} s_{ini}} \quad (2)$$

Here, s_{ini} is the initial value of parameter s ($s_{ini} = 0.999$ in this study). Parameter s is calculated as a function of the relative displacements.

$$s = \min\left(s_{\min}, \max\left(0, 1 - |\tilde{\Delta}|\right)\right) \quad (3)$$

$$\text{where } \tilde{\Delta} = \left\{ \Delta_n / \Delta_{nc}, \quad \Delta_t / \Delta_{tc}, \quad \Delta_b / \Delta_{bc} \right\}^T$$

The cohesive elements defined above act as follows ((a) through (c)).

- a) A cohesive element acts as a penalty element, maintaining the continuity of displacement at the element interface while $s = s_{ini}$.
- b) The parameter s becomes small according to the relative displacement once the cohesive element is stressed beyond its strength ($0 < s < s_{ini}$).
- c) A cohesive element generates a crack surface when it absorbs the energy equal to the critical energy release rate ($s = 0$).
- d) $s = s_{ini}$ is temporarily assigned to express the contact state if the corresponding cohesive element is under compression.

Thus, the parameter s represents the residual strength of the cohesive element.

Next, we present the formulation for a finite-element analysis with cohesive elements. The virtual work for the analytical region V including the cohesive zone S_{coh} is as follows.

$$\int_V \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \delta \mathbf{E} dV + \int_{S_{coh}} \mathbf{T} \cdot \delta \boldsymbol{\Delta} dS = \int_{S_t} \mathbf{f} \cdot \delta \mathbf{u} dS \quad (4)$$

Here, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the stress tensor, \mathbf{E} is the strain tensor, \mathbf{u} is the displacement vector, \mathbf{f} is the external force vector on the prescribed boundary S_t , and δ denotes the virtual component. The following relationship is obtained for the relative displacement $\boldsymbol{\Delta}$ in the cohesive elements for delamination.

$$\boldsymbol{\Delta} = \begin{Bmatrix} \Delta_n \\ \Delta_t \\ \Delta_b \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & \frac{t_l}{2} & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \frac{t_u}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & \frac{t_l}{2} & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \frac{t_u}{2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_l \\ \hat{\mathbf{u}}_u \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{L} \begin{Bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_l \\ \hat{\mathbf{u}}_u \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{where } \hat{\mathbf{u}} = \{\hat{u} \quad \hat{v} \quad \hat{w} \quad \theta_x \quad \theta_y\}^T$$

Here, t_l and t_u are the thicknesses of the lower and upper layers of delamination. Similar equations between $\boldsymbol{\Delta}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{u}}$ are obtained for transverse cracks and splits considering their deformation modes. The displacement vector of an element, $\{\hat{\mathbf{u}}_l \quad \hat{\mathbf{u}}_u\}^T$, is calculated from shape functions N^i and nodal displacement vector $\hat{\mathbf{U}}_e$.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{u}}_l \\ \hat{\mathbf{u}}_u \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} N^1 & N^2 & N^3 & N^4 & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & N^1 & N^2 & N^3 & N^4 \end{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{U}}_e = \mathbf{N}_{coh} \hat{\mathbf{U}}_e \quad (6)$$

$$N^i = N^i \mathbf{I}_5, \quad \mathbf{I}_5: \text{unit matrix } (5 \times 5)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{U}}_e = \{\hat{\mathbf{U}}_l^1 \quad \hat{\mathbf{U}}_l^2 \quad \hat{\mathbf{U}}_l^3 \quad \hat{\mathbf{U}}_l^4 \quad \hat{\mathbf{U}}_u^1 \quad \hat{\mathbf{U}}_u^2 \quad \hat{\mathbf{U}}_u^3 \quad \hat{\mathbf{U}}_u^4\}^T$$

With the above details, the matrix form of the virtual work principal can be represented by

$$\delta \hat{\mathbf{U}}^T \mathbf{K} \hat{\mathbf{U}} = \delta \hat{\mathbf{U}}^T \mathbf{f} \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{K} = \mathbf{K}_M + \mathbf{K}_{coh} \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_M = \int_{V_M} \mathbf{B}_M^T \mathbf{D}_M \mathbf{B}_M dV \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{coh} = \int_{S_{coh}} \mathbf{N}_{coh}^T \mathbf{L}^T \bar{\mathbf{D}}_{coh} \mathbf{L} \mathbf{N}_{coh} dS \quad (10)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{U}}$ is the nodal displacement vector; \mathbf{f} is the external force vector; \mathbf{K} , \mathbf{B} , and \mathbf{D} are the stiffness matrix, strain-displacement matrix and constitutive coefficients. Suffixes M and coh denote the Mindlin plate elements and the cohesive element.

Equation (7) is nonlinear since the stiffness matrix of cohesive elements \mathbf{K}_{coh} varies with the relative displacement. We used a direct-iteration method [7] to solve the nonlinear equation.

In order to express the damage growth due to the cyclic loads, this study introduces the concept of damage mechanics proposed by Kachanov [5] into each cohesive element. The following equation is applied for the residual strength parameter s of cohesive elements which are in the damage process zone and under tension [8].

$$\frac{ds}{dN} = -\alpha \frac{F^\beta}{s^\gamma} \quad (11)$$

$$F = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\tau_n}{\tau_{n \max}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_t}{\tau_{t \max}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_b}{\tau_{b \max}}\right)^2} \quad (12)$$

Here, α , β and γ are phenomenology parameters to reproduce the damage growth, and a dimensional parameter F is introduced to express the stress state at the crack tip. N denotes the number of cycles.

In this simulation, first, the deformation and the stress field at the maximum stress are calculated with Eq. (7). Second, the change of the residual strength parameter s of cohesive elements during the ΔN steps is estimated by Eq. (11). These two steps are repeated in this simulation so that the damage state at N cycles is simulated. The longitudinal strain distribution of optical fiber is calculated with the strain field mentioned above. As mentioned later, the debonding of optical fiber may grow as the number of cycles increases. To take the debonding into consideration, the longitudinal strain is assumed to be constant based on the bridging model in the ceramics matrix composites. Therefore, it is assumed that the friction at the interface between fiber and matrix does not work.

Once the strain distribution of the embedded optical fiber is analyzed, the reflection spectrum of the FBG sensor can be solved by a coupled mode equation. For the non-uniform FBG sensor, the grating period Λ and the effective refractive index of the core n_{eff} are expressed as functions of the longitudinal strain ε_f by

$$\Lambda = (1 + \varepsilon_f) \Lambda_0 \quad (13)$$

$$n_{eff} = n_0 + \Delta n = n_0 - \frac{n_0^3}{2} \{p_{12} - \nu_f (p_{11} + p_{12})\} \varepsilon_f \quad (14)$$

In these equations, Λ_0 is the initial period of the index modulation, ν_f is the Poisson's ratio of glass, and p_{11} and p_{12} are the strain-optic coefficients where indices 1 and 2 mean the axial and transverse directions of the optical fiber. Using these non-uniform FBG profiles, the reflection spectrum can be easily solved by the transfer matrix method [3,9]. Therefore, the obtained reflection spectrum naturally depends on the damage pattern occurring in the laminate.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As mentioned above, Fig. 3 illustrates the schematic figure of the model simulating the fatigue damage in the cross-ply laminates and the reflection spectrum. The material properties are listed in Table 1 and the cohesive parameters are in Table 2. The parameters used in Eq. (11) are $\alpha = 1.0 \times 10^{-5}$ for transverse cracks and splits, $\alpha_d = 5.0 \times 10^{-5}$ for delamination, and $\beta = \gamma = 4.0$ for all damage types; these have been discussed in our previous paper [10]. The gage length of FBG sensor embedded into the laminate are 12.5 mm and the gage section is set up within the region $0 \leq x \leq 12.5$; $y = 3.86$. The parameters of the optical fiber and the FBG sensor to calculate the reflection spectrum are listed in Table 3. In this analysis, the birefringence effect due to the thermal residual strain is also considered.

Figure 4 presents the distribution of the damaged cohesive elements due to the cyclic loading. The simulated damage pattern agreed well with the experimental results depicted in Fig. 1. The analyzed reflection spectrum is illustrated in Fig. 2 (blue line). The analyzed reflection spectrum before the fatigue test agreed with the measured one by considering the birefringence effect due to the thermal residual strain. The width of reflection spectrum became broad due to the stress concentration of the hole when the load was applied. In addition, the shape of reflection spectrum changed with the damage extension. However, the analysis that did not consider the debonding of the optical fiber was not consistent with the experimental results. Then, as mentioned above, we considered the debonding of the optical fiber and reproduced the reflection spectrum by adjusting the debonding length (Fig. 2 red line). Concretely speaking, the analyzed

Table 1 Material properties used in the analysis.

<i>For CFRP</i>	
Longitudinal Young's modulus (GPa)	140
Transverse Young's modulus (GPa)	7.4
In-plane shear modulus (GPa)	4.5
Out-of-plane shear modulus (GPa)	3.5
In-plane Poisson's ratio	0.356
Out-of-plane Poisson's ratio	0.49
Longitudinal thermal expansion coefficient ($\times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$)	0.3
Transverse thermal expansion coefficient ($\times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$)	36.5
<i>For optical fiber</i>	
Young's modulus of glass (GPa)	73.1
Young's modulus of coating (GPa)	1.47
Thermal expansion coefficient of glass ($\times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$)	0.5
Thermal expansion coefficient of coating ($\times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$)	60

Table 2 Properties of the cohesive elements.

<i>For splits and transverse cracks</i>	
In-plane tensile strength (MPa)	76
In-plane shear strength (MPa)	100
Out-of-plane shear strength (MPa)	100
Mode I critical energy release rate (J/m ²)	150
Mode II critical energy release rate (J/m ²)	300
Mode III critical energy release rate (J/m ²)	300
<i>For delamination</i>	
In-plane tensile strength (MPa)	30
In-plane shear strength (MPa)	60
Out-of-plane shear strength (MPa)	60
Mode I critical energy release rate (J/m ²)	200
Mode II critical energy release rate (J/m ²)	600
Mode III critical energy release rate (J/m ²)	600

Table 3 Optical properties of the apodized FBG sensor.

Gage length (mm)	12.5
Initial center wavelength (nm)	1550.28
Initial refractive index of the core	1.4490
Depth of index modulation	4.0×10^{-4}
Strain-optic coefficients p_{11}	0.113
Strain-optic coefficients p_{12}	0.252

Fig. 4 Simulated damage patterns of the holed CFRP cross-ply laminate under cyclic loading.

reflection spectrum had two peaks and its width was close to the measured reflection spectrum when the debonding length was assumed to be 5.5 mm at $N = 10^3$. Moreover,

the analyzed reflection spectrum had one large peak and its width was close to the measured spectrum when the debonding length was assumed to be 8.0 mm at $N = 10^4$ and 15.0 mm at $N = 10^5$. These analyzed results with debonding of the optical fiber were consistent with the experiments. This implied that the debonding grew slowly as the number of cyclic load increased. In addition, the debonding length was consistent with the damage area observed in experiments. Thus, it was found that the debonding of the optical fiber could occur since the strain around damages was high. Naturally, the debonding was an important factor to detect the damage during the cyclic loading because this may limit the monitoring period in the application of FBG sensor.

CONCLUSIONS

This study experimentally and numerically investigates evaluation of fatigue damage progress in holed CFRP laminates by using embedded fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensors. First, tensile fatigue tests were conducted for a holed CFRP cross-ply laminate with an embedded FBG sensor; the damage pattern near the hole and the reflection spectrum of the FBG sensor were observed in detail. Furthermore, the reflection spectrum was analyzed by a finite-element based fatigue simulation with cohesive elements and by an optical analysis for the FBG sensor. We clarified the mechanism of the change in the reflection spectrum due to the damage extension, and discussed the damage monitoring for the CFRP laminate under cyclic loading based on the information from the embedded FBG sensor. Especially, we found that the debonding of the optical fiber could occur since the strain around damages was high. Naturally, the debonding of the optical fiber was an important factor to detect the damage during the cyclic loading because this may limit the monitoring period in the application of FBG sensor.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

One of the authors (S. Y.) acknowledges the support from Mazda Foundation under a research grant.

References

1. Spearing SM, Beaumont PWR. Fatigue damage mechanics of composite materials. I: Experimental measurement of damage and post-fatigue properties. *Compos Sci Technol* 1992; 44(2):159–168.
2. Okabe Y, Yashiro S, Kosaka T, Takeda N. Detection of transverse cracks in CFRP composites using embedded fiber Bragg grating sensors. *Smart Mater Struct* 2000; 9(6): 832–838.
3. Yashiro S, Takeda N, Okabe T, Sekine H. A new approach to predicting multiple damage states in composite laminates with embedded FBG sensors. *Compos Sci Technol* 2005; 65(3–4): 659–667.
4. Okabe Y, Yashiro S, Tsuji R, Mizutani T, Takeda N. Effect of thermal residual stress on the reflection spectrum from fiber Bragg grating sensors embedded in CFRP laminates. *Composites Part A* 2002; 33(7) 991–999.

5. Skrzypek J, Ganczarski A. Modeling of material damage and failure of structures. Springer-Verlag; 1999.
6. Geubelle PH, Baylor JS. Impact-induced delamination of composites: a 2D simulation. *Composites B* 1998; 29(5): 589–602.
7. Owen DRJ, Hinton E. Finite elements in plasticity. Swansea: Pineridge Press; 1980.
8. Okabe T, Yashiro S. Numerical simulation for predicting fatigue damage progress in CFRP laminates by using cohesive elements (in Japanese). *Trans Japan Soc Mech Engineers A* 2009; 75(751): 304–309.
9. Huang S, LeBlanc M, Ohn MM, Measures RM. Bragg intragrating structural sensing. *Appl Opt* 1995; 34(22): 5003–5009.
10. Yashiro S, Okabe T. Numerical prediction of fatigue damage progress in holed CFRP laminates using cohesive elements (in Japanese). *Trans Japan Soc Mech Engineers A* 2009; 75(751): 310-315.